

About encouraging children to read books

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There is abundant information about encouraging children to read books. In this article, we explore how the formation and improvement of a child's interest in reading has been thoroughly studied not only in modern psychology but also in the heritage of Eastern thinkers. Our attention was particularly drawn to the ideas put forward by our scholars Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Rayhan Beruni, which serve as an important theoretical foundation for stimulating interest in reading through psychological mechanisms today. Al-Farabi distinguished between two stages of cognition - sensory and mental, emphasizing the high role and importance of the human intellect in the process of cognition. He substantiated that personal perfection is achieved through the pursuit of knowledge, being erudite, and correctly directing one's mind. The thinker urged people to be educated and presented instructive ideas about the role of students in society and their inherent qualities.

According to Al-Farabi, a teacher must work tirelessly and sincerely to educate students and impart knowledge to them, as only then will students become interested in learning and acquiring knowledge. Thus, the development of an individual's interest in reading is closely linked to the psychological influence of the teacher. If a teacher has a perfect grasp of their subject and possesses pedagogical skills, they can introduce their students to the subject effectively, and students who become interested in the subject will certainly strive to read additional sources. Al-Farabi deeply analyzed the qualities inherent in a student's personality and recognized that the teacher plays an important role as a means of fostering interest in reading [95].

Therefore, providing a child with information about books is truly the best gift, but not everyone wants to love reading equally. Some prefer reading books, some like listening (mp3), some enjoy watching videos, that's why it is necessary to identify children's interests and guide them towards reading books. Many parents force their children to study both at school and at home. But this is incorrect. You can't force a child to be interested in books. Instead, it's better to use several effective techniques.

Indeed, why do modern children need books? Previously, books were practically the only source of information and one of the best forms of recreation. Today? The sea of information and entertainment fills our psyche through television screens and computer monitors. Yes, a moving image is always better than a static one because it creates the illusion of live communication, and frees us from loneliness.

You press a button, and a wave of someone else's joys, fears, hopes, and disappointments enters your life, distracting you from everyday reality. How many pages of a book do you need to read to experience the same emotions? However, the problem is that culture (books, feature films, art) shapes a person's personality, especially during childhood, therefore it is necessary to teach children to read and love books. If you really want to introduce your child to books, it is advisable to follow these recommendations: **Read books to your child from birth.** Yes, the baby doesn't yet understand the words, but the poems read by the mother "speak" to the baby about their closeness. The mother's voice and tone soothe the child. From 10 months to one and a half years, the child's vocabulary begins to form. After all, the child actively explores the world with all their senses. However, when reading a book, do not exceed the attention span of more than four minutes. From the age of two, the child perceives individual words and phrases as a story, and by the age of three, they become not only a listener but also an active conversationalist. During this time, the child develops a desire to read again develops. Don't read them a book for more than 20 minutes. This is the maximum a child can endure at this age.

Turn reading into a game. If you want to introduce your child to books from an early age, conduct this process as a game. "Remember, you will be the smartest," "When you grow up, you will be the best essay writer" - such arguments don't work. Eliminate these kinds of statements from your speech. **Don't be afraid of repetition.** Don't worry or be surprised if your child has been asking you to read the same book at night for several years. It simply represents psychological comfort for them. You might also have such a book. If you read it now, you will return to the comfortable state you experienced in childhood. You might even want to introduce this book to your child, but there's no guarantee that it will be the same for them as it is for you. All of this is very individual. As a rule, reading the same books every day "ends" at eight years old. **Have them memorize poems.** The optimal time for this is - the period from birth to eight years! This won't require much effort from you, as memorization is easy for children at this

age. In middle school, if you haven't developed this skill before, it requires some effort.

Allow the child to choose literature. Let your child select books that interest them. Every book is beneficial in some way. Prose helps develop speech skills, while poetry cultivates a sense of rhythm. A familiar book creates psychological comfort, while an unfamiliar one provides new knowledge. Fairy tale plots enrich imagination, and realistic plots enrich life experience. Short stories teach concise narration, while long stories train memory.

Children don't want to read the recommended literature at school. This is because it's difficult for every child to prefer the same thing. Some like short stories with a clear beginning, quick progression, and definite ending. Others don't see the point in getting to know a short story's protagonist because they're not ready to say goodbye to them so quickly. They need to spend more time with the character.

Don't force your child to read. The desire to read forms from within, so it's risky to force a child to read from the age of five or six. Generally, the word "must" should be used cautiously, at a more mature age, i.e., starting from the 5th-6th grades, and only in relation to school literature.

If a child doesn't want to read, there's nothing wrong with that. Parents often worry about their child going to school without knowing how to read. They are afraid. Everything depends on the teacher. Some educators emphasize that if a child is brought to school at a certain level of preparedness, they become bored with repetitive school activities and their attitudes towards learning change.

Filling the environment with books can lead to boredom. A father brings many books for his children as a holiday gift and tells them, "I brought you a present." The children surround him with curiosity, but when they see the books, they respond: "Thank you for the books, but where's the gift?"

In our childhood, books were always scarce. Therefore, there was a great desire to read them. This experience may be valid. Especially when you want to read something and it's not available, it leads to an increased desire.

Discuss the books you've read with your children. Parents rarely read books in front of their children. Use these moments to talk with them about the book you're currently reading, or even try reading excerpts. You can also discuss books with others in front of your children.

Read aloud. Record your voice on a voice recorder. Parents spend the whole day at work, and if they read aloud to their children for at least ten minutes while at home, this becomes a strong bond that holds relationships together. A

phone is not suitable for voice recording, as it constantly demands attention. A voice recorder has only one button - you can turn it on and off. Of course, there are many such devices, and you need to choose which one is most suitable for you and your children.

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